

Students' Grammatical Errors in Writing Recount Text by the Tenth Grade of SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung

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ABSTRACT: It is often found out that many students commonly make grammar mistakes in their learning especially in writing. This study aimed to find the types of errors made by grade X students of SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung in writing Recount Text. Theoretically, this research was conducted to identify, classify and show the proportion of each type of errors made by students. The type of research used was qualitative research with descriptive methods. The research subjects were 25 students of SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung who were in the first semester of grade X. The instrument used was documentation of students' writings about recount text. All grammatical errors that appeared in student writings were analyzed using the Surface Strategy Taxonomy introduced by Dulay et.al. The findings showed that the total error was 171 errors. Most errors were omission (70 errors/41%), second place was substitution error (69 errors/40%), third place was addition error (20 errors/12%), and the last was permutation error (12 errors/7%). Based on these results, it was summed up that students still experienced great difficulties in learning the grammar structure in the writing process.

KEYWORDS: Error, Error analysis, Grammatical error, Types of grammatical errors, Writing

INTRODUCTION

Language is very important in human life. By language people can express their mind, ideas and thought. Language is the systematic and conventional use of sounds (or signs or written symbols) for the purpose of communication or self-expression (Crystal, 1995). People need language to express themselves when they interact in the society. Writing is one of aspects in English language which is very important to be learned. Writing skills must be practiced and learned through experience. Writing is a process that guides people to express their opinions, views, suggestions through the words. Everyone can write anything in all languages because language is like a role, and writing is the way. Writing requires ideas, thought, emotions, or experience to transfer and send them into a paper to create the meaningful text.

It is important to note that some people assume that writing takes the highest position in difficulty among four skills in English language. One of the reasons is writing needs a special skill to string words to be understood by the reader. King (1999) argues that if you want to be a writer, you must do two things above all others: read a lot and write a lot. It shows that to be writer, you have to read a lot, such as books, articles, newspaper, magazine etc. So, you can write well. Actually, writing needs well knowledge and hard thinking when the students produce words, sentences, paragraph at the same time with good English grammatical. However, it is often found out that many students commonly make grammar mistakes in their learning especially in writing. The mistakes are done repeatedly because they do not have the correction from the teachers which is further called as error.

Errors in foreign language teaching especially in English are the cases which are difficult enough to avoid. It is essential for the teacher to give error analysis in students' writing. Error analysis is an activity to identify, classify and interpret or describe the errors made by someone in speaking or in writing and it is carried out to obtain information on common difficulties faced by someone in speaking or in writing English sentences. B. Niati (2019) states that if the teacher only teaches English to the learners passively (reading and listening), the students' speaking and writing skills will not improve optimally. Therefore, it is an important thing to learn and understand about errors, especially in error analysis.

According to Khansir (2012), Error analysis is a type of linguistic analysis that focuses on the errors by learners made. Learning errors is a must to improve the writing skills in English, and also to avoid the errors in writing. There are some causes of the errors in writing made by the students. They can be shocked because of the vocabularies, punctuation or pronunciation, and many more. On the other side, errors occur because of overgeneralization, misunderstanding, and wrong concepts hypothesized.

Brown (1980) offers another concept for error analysis. According to Brown, error analysis is the act of observing, analyzing, and categorizing deviations from the second language's rules in order to identify the learner's operating systems. It appears that this idea is similar to Crystal (1987), who stated that error analysis is a method for identifying, categorizing, and systematically interpreting the unacceptable forms produced by students learning a foreign language using any of the principles and procedures offered by linguistics. Based on the definitions mentioned above, it highlights the fact that error analysis is a process used to recognize, categorize, interpret, or describe mistakes that people make when speaking or writing, and it is carried out to learn about common challenges people encounter when speaking or writing English sentences.

There are four descriptive taxonomies which are commonly used as the basis for error classification; (1) Linguistic Category Taxonomy, (2) Surface Strategy Taxonomy, (3) Comparative Taxonomy, and (4) Communicative Effect Taxonomy. However, in this study, the researcher classified the errors based on Surface Strategy Taxonomy. In Dulay, Burt, and Krashen's Surface Structure Taxonomy (1982 cited in Ellis and Barkhuizen, 2005, p. 61), four categories were proposed to explain how sentences deviate from the correct forms because the learners change the surface structure. Those categories are omission, addition, substitution, and permutation.

Omission error is described by the absence of an item that must appear in a well-formed utterance in spoken or in written form. Example: The person on the stage. It is incorrect because the student omit auxiliary "is". On the contrary, addition error is typified by the presence of an item, which must not appear in a well-formed utterance in spoken or sentence in written form. Example: She does not performs well. In this sentence, the student add morpheme "s" in the verb "performs". Meanwhile, substitution error is characterized by the use of the wrong form of morpheme or structure. Example: The students is in the class. The sentence is incorrect because the student use auxiliary "is" for plural noun. The last error, permutation error, is portrayed by incorrect placement of morpheme or group of morphemes in an utterance in spoken or sentence in written form. Example: Comes the teacher to the class. (incorrect).

There have been some previous researches regarding to the error analysis in student's writing. Setiyorini (2020) conducted a research about the grammatical error analysis found in students' composition. The research shows that the most dominant error found in students' essays is substitution followed by omission, addition, and permutation. Kharmilah (2019), states that it is omission in the highest position. The populations of these two researches are third and four semester students of English Department in university which means that they have already learned writing in English in a long time. However, they still produced all form of errors.

Regarding to the matters previously, the researcher is interested in analyzing the errors made by the student in writing Recount Text especially related to their personal experience in joining Education Fair in SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung. The research questions are:

1. What types of errors do the students do in writing Recount Text?
2. What is the dominant type of error made by the students in writing Recount Text?

METHODS

The term research can mean any sort of careful, systematic, patient study and investigation in some field of knowledge. A research design is set up to decide on, among other issues, how to collect further data, analyze and interpret them, and finally, to provide an answer to the problem. In this research, the researcher used a descriptive case study. A descriptive case study aims to present detailed information on a specific phenomenon to get a deep understanding of the case (Heigham & Croker, 2009). In this study, the researchers presented detailed information about grammatical errors found in the essay writing.

The subjects of the study were 25 students of Grade X SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung. The data sources of this research were documents. The documents were in the form of essays written by 25 students of Grade X SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung. The analysis unit is the sentences found in essays written the students. The researcher used a test to collect the data.

In collecting the data, the researcher displayed the topic of the essay *Personal experience in joining Immanuel Education Fair*. Then, the researcher asked the students to compose an essay based on the topic. Finally, they submitted their essays. The researchers analyzed the data by using some steps; reading the results of students' essays, highlighting grammatical errors in students' essays, categorizing grammatical errors found in students' essays, giving explanations of the types of grammatical errors found in students'

essays, gathering and counting the result and putting it into the table, calculating the percentage of each error found in students' essays, interpreting and explaining the result, and drawing the conclusion from the result. The percentage used the formula as follows:

$$P = f/n \times 100\%$$

Note:

P = percentage of the number of error

f = frequency of each type of error

n = number of error

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

In this part, the researcher presents the findings of the analysis grammatical errors found in essays about Recount Text telling past experiences in joining Immanuel Education Fair written by 25 students of grade X of SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung.

Table 1. The Recapitulation of Types of Grammatical Errors Found in Students' Essays

Types of errors	Number	Percentage
Omission	70	41%
Addition	20	12%
Substitution	69	40%
Permutation	12	7%
Total	171	100%

The table portrayed in the result of the study clearly. There were 171 errors which were classified into 70 omissions, 20 additions, 69 substitutions, and 12 permutation errors. The result of the study showed that the most frequently error made by the students was omission which consisted of 70 errors or 41%. It was followed by error of substitution with percentage 40%, error in addition was 12%, and error of permutation was 7%. There was no significant difference in number of error in Omission and Substitution.

Table 2. The Percentage of Students' Errors in Omission

Types of errors	Indicators	Total	Percentage
Omission	Omission of Punctuation	46	66%
	Omission of Verb Inflexion	4	6%
	Omission of Subject	8	11%
	Omission of object	4	6%
	Omission of -ing	4	6%
	Omission of Auxiliary	4	6%
Total		70	100%

As shown in table 2, errors in Omission were mostly dominated by the omission of punctuation 66%. These punctuations referred to the use of commas and full stops in the sentences. Omission of verb inflexion, omission of object, omission of -ing, and omission of auxiliary took the same percentages 6%. Omission of subject was 8%.

Table 3. The Percentage of Students' Errors in Addition

Types of errors	Indicators	Total	Percentage
Addition	Addition of Article	4	20%
	Addition of verb Inflexion	4	20%
	Addition of Conjunction	12	60%
Total		20	100%

Table 3 described the percentage of errors in addition. Addition of conjunction was in 60 % followed by addition of article ^{20%} and addition of verb inflexion 20%.

Table 4. The Percentage of Students' Errors in Substitution

Types of errors	Indicators	Total	Percentage
Substitution	Substitution of Verb	53	77%
	Substitution of Preposition	16	23%
Total		69	100%

Table 4 was the percentage of errors in substitution where substitution of Verb was 77%. The researcher found that this finding referred to the use of present verb (infinitive) instead of past verb. Recount text is a text that retelling past experience. So, it was supposed to be written in the past verb form.

Table 5. The Percentage of Students' Errors in Permutation

Types of errors	Indicators	Total	Percentage
Permutation	Permutation of sentence pattern	12	100%
Total		12	100%

Students' errors in permutation only occurred in the form permutation of sentence.

DISCUSSION

From the identification and distribution of students errors in writing recount text essays about personal experience joining Immanuel Education fair, there were 171 errors which were classified into 70 omissions, 20 additions, 69 substitutions, and 12 permutation errors. The result of the study showed that the most frequently error made by the students was omission which consisted of 70 errors or 41%. It was followed by error of substitution with percentage 40%, error in addition was 12%, and error of permutation was 7%.

a. Omission errors

Omission is the error which is characterized by the absence of an item that must appear in a well-formed utterance. Most students committed errors by omitting punctuation, omission of subject, omission of object, omission of -ing, and omission of auxiliary. The following are the example of omission made by the students.

1. *"Then as the final event for the day they held mobile legend tournament"* (paragraph 2 line 10-11).
In this sentence, the students did not use commas and full stop. The correct sentence should be *"Then, as the final event for the day, they held mobile legend tournament."*
2. *"The culinary team is preparing the to sell"* (paragraph 1, line 3). The student omitted the object. The correct sentence should be *"The culinary team is preparing the food to sell."*
3. *"then went home"* (paragraph 3, line 24). The student omitted punctuation and subject. The correct sentence should be *"Then, we went home."*

b. Addition errors

Addition errors are characterized by the presence of an extra item which must not appear in a well-formed utterance. The most percentage error of addition made by the students was addition of Conjunction. The following were the examples of addition errors made by the students.

1. *"and what was no less exciting was the arrival of another universities and was warmly welcomed with traditional dance SigeH Pengunten and asked for signatures from the campus"* (paragraph 1). The student used conjunction *and* repeatedly. The correct sentence should be *"What was no less exciting was the arrival of some universities. They were warmly welcomed with traditional dance SigeH Pengunten. Then, we were obliged to ask for signatures from those universities."*
2. *"On the October 26th, there were several competitions."* (Paragraph 2, line 1). The student's error was adding the article *the*. The correct sentence should be *"On October 26th, there were several competitions."*

c. Substitution errors

The substitution uses the incorrect form of a word in a sentence or an utterance. The errors made by the students in this part mostly referred to the incorrect form of verbs. There were 53 (77%) errors. The following were the examples of substitution errors made by the students.

1. “*We dress up and wear our own clothes*”(paragraph 2, line 7). There were incorrect forms of verb in this sentence because the sentence was written in the context of retelling past experience. The correct sentence should be “*We dressed up and wore our own clothes.*”
2. “*We call this 10th grade project or P-5*”(paragraph 1, line 2). Same as the first example, it was found that there was incorrect form of verb in this sentence. The correct sentence should be “*We called this 10th grade project or P-5.*”

d. Permutation errors

The permutation is the placement of a morpheme or a word in a sentence or an utterance which is not arranged correctly. There was only one permutation errors made by the students in this part; permutation of sentence. The following was the example.

“*On the October 26, Immanuel High School in the morning at 07.30 to 09.00 we watched the opening of the Immanuel High School education fair*” (paragraph 2, line 1 - 2). The correct sentence should be “*On October 26th, we watched the opening of the Immanuel High School Education Fair at 07.30 in the morning.*” Besides arranging into a good order, the phrase “*Immanuel High School*” in “*On October 26, Immanuel High School in the morning at 07.30 ...*” should be omitted.

Based on the explanation, the research questions in this study were answered clearly. The types of errors the students do in writing Recount Text telling their experiences in joining Immanuel Education Fair were Omission Errors, Addition Errors, Substitution Errors, and Permutation Errors. The dominant type of error made by the students was Omission Errors 41% which was almost the same as in Substitution Errors 40%.

There were similarities and differences between the results of this study compared to the previous study. The research by Setiyorini (2020) showed that the most dominant error found in students’ essays was substitution followed by omission, addition, and permutation. Kharmilah (2019) reported that it was omission in the highest position which was continued by permutation (misformation), addition, and substitution (misordering). The findings revealed that the students produced all forms of errors in their writing task. Similar to those researches, this study found that all forms of errors were produced by the students. However, the orders of the errors made were different. From the highest to the lowest percentage, the orders were omission, substitution, addition, and permutation.

CONCLUSION

It is crucial for the lecturer to do the error analysis to detect students’ errors in their essays. Based on the research result, the total of grammatical errors devoted by 25 of grade X students of SMA Immanuel Bandar Lampung were 171 errors. The total number of errors for each error type was 70 (omission), 20 (addition), 69 (substitution), and 12 (permutation). The analysis result showed that the percentage for each error type was 41% (omission), 12 (addition), 40 (substitution), and 7 (permutation). The researchers came up to the conclusion that the most dominant error was Omission. The percentage of error proved it. However, there was no significant difference in number between omission (41%) and substitution (40%)

The contribution of this research was as a portrait to the teachers in order to be more concern on teaching grammar in writing. First, the teachers could give enrichment based on students’ errors. The teachers should repeat and emphasize the materials related to students’ errors, explain the materials clearly, and develop the exercises to enhance students’ understanding and knowledge. Furthermore, through this study, the teachers could understand students’ grammar competence.

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